

Breast Cancer Prediction using Machine Learning Algorithms - A Deep Learning Approach

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Abstract

Breast Cancer is the most deadly and commonly diagnosed cancer in women globally. Early diagnosis and treatment of breast cancer increases the chance of a five-year survival rate by 99%. Recent technological and computational advancement have led to the discovery of machine learning algorithms for the analysis of complex data. Machine learning algorithms have been widely applied for the analysis of breast cancer data. In this essay, we propose to implement machine learning algorithms, using a deep learning approach, for automatic detection and prediction of breast cancer using mammogram images. To achieve this, we implement transfer learning on a deep learning algorithm called Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). Two datasets of breast cancer images are analyzed using three CNN models in existing deep learning frameworks. The models perform a binary and multiclass classification task on the images. Experimental results showed that CNN models can accurately identify and predict breast cancer when provided with a large and balanced dataset.

Keywords: Breast Cancer, Deep Learning, Convolutional Neural Network.

Declaration

I, the undersigned, hereby declare that the work contained in this research project is my original work, and that any work done by others or by myself previously has been acknowledged and referenced accordingly.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Cancer is a general term for a large group of diseases that can affect body parts. Also, it is the second leading cause of death globally ([World Health Organisation](#)). Cancer arises from the transformation of normal cells into tumor cells in a multistage process. Tumorous cells can either be cancerous (malignant) or non-cancerous (benign). According to statistics by the International Agency for Research on Cancer, cancer cases increased by 28% between 2006 and 2016, and there will be 2.7 million new cancer cases emerging in 2030. In particular, breast cancer is one of the most common and deadly in women accounting for 2.9 million death cases in 2018 ([World Health Organisation](#)).

Breast cancer refers to the development of a malignant tumor that arises from cells in the breast. The tumors invade surrounding tissues or spread (metastasize) to distant areas of the body ([American Cancer Society](#)). The most common symptoms of breast cancer are lumps in the breast, dimpling, nipple retraction amongst other factors. The survival rate of breast cancer mostly depends on early diagnostic techniques of the disease and improved treatment tools ([Sekaran et al., 2018](#)). Some of the most important tools for the detection of breast cancer include the use of mammography, magnetic resonance imaging, and biopsy. Mammography is a type of specialized medical imaging that uses a low-dose x-ray system to scan the breast and is considered the most reliable method for screening the breast for any sign of abnormality.

Asides detecting tumors in the breast, there is a need for medical practitioners to accurately diagnose breast cancer and proffer the required treatment options. Computer-Aided Detection (CAD) is a technology that has been used over the years, as a tool to assist medical practitioners in cancer diagnosis ([Halalli and Makandar, 2018](#)). Recent advancement in technology has led to the development of more advanced techniques for the detection and prediction of breast cancer.

Machine learning is a technique that can be used to identify, detect and classify abnormality in the breast. Standard machine learning techniques require the extraction of features such as shape and size of tumors from images, to perform a classification task. However, the feature extraction task requires experience and expertise. Consequently, deep learning is a subset of machine learning that does not rely on feature extraction but performs automatic feature extraction directly from images.

Deep learning algorithms have been developed to perform classification tasks for pattern recognition, computer vision and image recognition ([Wang et al., 2017](#)). In particular, a deep learning algorithm known as a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is popularly known for exceptional performance in image recognition task. In this essay, three CNN models will be utilized for the detection and prediction of tumors located in the breast.

1.2 Aims and Objective

The objective of this essay is to exploit CNN models for the detection and prediction of normal and abnormal tumors found in the breast, using images from mammograms. Three major CNN models will be implemented for the classification of breast tumors by the extraction of features through a hierarchical learning process. The experiments will be performed using Keras, a deep learning framework.

For the first experiment, a binary classification task will be performed on the Mammographic Image Analysis Society (MIAS) dataset. Secondly, a multiclass classification task will be performed on the Digital

Database for Screening Mammography (DDSM) dataset. The efficiency of each model's performance on the test set will be measured using validation techniques and different evaluation metrics.

1.3 Essay Structure

This essay is structured thus: In Chapter 2, an introduction to machine learning and deep learning will be provided. Also, CNN operations, the network's learning process, and CNN models will be described. Chapter 3 consists of a description of the methodology and evaluation criteria used for the analysis of each chosen CNN model. Chapter 4 provides the details of the experiments for each dataset and discusses the results. Finally, Chapter 5 presents the conclusion, possible future work, and limitations encountered in this essay.

2. Deep Learning for Image Processing

This chapter discusses the deep learning architecture and deep neural network models. Furthermore, we will discuss the operations and learning process involved in a CNN model as a deep neural network as well as the different CNN models to be used for our experiment.

2.1 Introduction to Machine Learning

In the field of computing and information technology, there has been a rapid increase and development of techniques that aid the identification and interpretation of complex and hidden patterns in data. Given these advancements, standard machine learning techniques have been developed to teach a machine to learn from a given dataset and make predictions based on what it has learned without being given a specific set of instructions or algorithms to follow (Ayodele, 2010). Several machine learning algorithms have been developed over the years, ranging from basic classifiers to artificial neural networks (Jatana, 2018).

An increase in the use of standard machine learning techniques such as support vector machine, decision tree and random forest for prediction and classification problems has resulted in an increase in the application of machine learning techniques in the medical field. These techniques are being used for disease identification, diagnosis in medical imaging and drug discovery, early prediction of cancer outcome, and medical research (Kouro et al., 2015).

For standard machine learning algorithms to achieve state-of-the-art performance, they require feature engineering. Feature engineering involves construction or transformation of features from a data. The process of feature transformation requires experience, dedication, and expertise from the engineer (Nargesian et al., 2017). The performance of these standard machine learning algorithms depend on how accurately each feature is discerned and extracted. The feature engineering process which requires a deliberate effort on the part of an engineer may sometimes result in mistakes. Deep learning is an advanced technique in machine learning that was developed to reduce the need for feature engineering when processing data. Deep learning algorithms automatically learn to extract useful features directly from data and make useful predictions using the extracted features.

2.2 Deep Learning for Medical Imaging

Deep learning, a subset of the machine learning field, is designed to learn hierarchically from a problem and perform classification based on the learned features (Deng, 2014). Deep learning algorithms utilize a layered structure of algorithms known as an Artificial Neural Network (ANN). The ANN's design was inspired by the structure of the biological neural network of the human brain (Manickam et al., 2017). A deep learning algorithm's ability to imitate how the human brain works by learning and making intelligent decisions on its own is what distinguishes it from standard machine learning algorithms.

A basic ANN structure shown in Figure 2.1 consists of interconnected neurons arranged in at least three layers. Each neuron in the network represents one aspect of the input data and each connection between neurons is associated with a weight that dictates the importance of an input value and a bias that controls the rate at which a neuron is fired. The layers of an ANN include the input layer, the hidden layers, and an output layer. The input layer receives raw input data and passes the input to the first hidden layer. The hidden layers perform mathematical computations on the input they receive.

The output layer receives an input from the preceding hidden layer, performs computation on the input and returns an output value.

An ANN with two or more hidden layers form a deep neural network. In a deep neural network, features are extracted hierarchically. The network initially learns low-level features and further combines the learned features to form more abstract representations as it progresses into each layer (Deng, 2014). Features may include shape, orientation, color, texture, position, and pixel values. Deep neural networks have achieved state-of-the-art performance in various fields such as computer vision, natural language processing, and medical diagnosis.

Figure 2.1: The structure of an ANN with input, hidden and output layers. Source: (Bre et al., 2017)

Deep learning has been applied in the field of image classification (Krishna et al., 2018), pattern recognition and other domains. Specifically, in the medical domain, deep learning plays a significant role in the diagnosis of disease, and assists medical practitioners in making informed decisions on treatment procedures after diagnosis of a disease (Abdelhafiz et al., 2019). Deep learning techniques were used by Lee et al. (2017) to identify metastatic breast cancer. Ragab et al. (2019) applied deep learning for the detection and classification of malignant and benign tumors in the breast. In this essay, a deep neural network will be applied for the prediction of normal and abnormal tumors detected in the breast, using images from mammograms.

2.2.1 Deep Neural Network Models. There are various types of neural network models that have been developed over the years for use in classification and regression problems, language processing, speech synthesis, and other relevant areas. Three major neural network models that have achieved good performance on varying problems will be described in this subsection.

- a) **Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP):** MLP is a simple neural network model composed of a minimum of three layers which include an input layer, one or more hidden layer(s) and an output layer. Layers of a fully connected MLP network is composed of nodes, each of these nodes is connected to every node in subsequent layers (Nazzal et al., 2008). During the training process, a learning algorithm is used to calculate the randomly initialized random weights in the hidden layer and adjusted gradually until the learning algorithm converges to a tolerable error approximation (Gallo, 2015). MLP is applicable in the area of pattern recognition, speech synthesis, image coding and compression.
- b) **Recurrent Neural Network (RNN):** RNN is a deep neural network that was designed to detect patterns in sequential data. A basic RNN structure consists of input, hidden and output layer. A major distinguishing factor of an RNN network is the presence of an hidden state which preserves sequential information (Salehinejad et al., 2018). The hidden state structure enables the network to preserve or store information from past inputs, process the past information and predict sequence

in the next time step (Jones). RNNs achieve a high rate of success in areas where the sequence of processed information is important; areas such as natural language processing, speech synthesis and machine translation (Gibson and Patterson, 2017).

- c) **Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)**: One of the most popular deep neural network is CNN. CNN mainly performs well on image data classification and computer vision attributable to the structure of the CNN. The structure of a CNN is composed of three layers which include the convolutional layer, the pooling (sub-sampling) layer and the fully connected (dense) layer (O'Shea and Nash, 2015) as shown in Figure 2.2. The major highlight of the excellent performance of a CNN network is the convolution process performed in the convolutional layer, hence the name convolutional neural network. This essay implements CNN models on mammogram images for detection and prediction of normal and abnormal tumors found in the breast. The operations involved during convolution are described in Section 2.3.

2.3 Convolutional Neural Network Architecture

There are four primary operations involved in the convolutional neural network. Those operations include convolution, non-linearity, pooling or sub-sampling and classification (fully connected layer).

Figure 2.2: The CNN architecture takes an input and passes it through a stack of convolutional layer, pooling layer and fully connected layer to produce the desired classes of output values.

2.3.1 Activation Functions. Activation functions transform the activation level of a unit into an output signal. Activation functions decide the output of a neuron based on the provided information (Nwankpa et al., 2018). Three most commonly used activation functions include:

- a) **Sigmoid Function**: The sigmoid function takes any range of real number and returns an output value which lies within the range of 0 and 1 (Nwankpa et al., 2018). Shown in Figure 2.3, it is mathematically defined by Equation 2.3.1.

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}. \quad (2.3.1)$$

- b) **Tanh Function**: Tanh is a zero centered function whose range lies between -1 and 1 given by Equation 2.3.2 and shown in Figure 2.3. It has a higher range of derivative than the sigmoid function which results in a better learning rate (Nwankpa et al., 2018).

$$f(x) = \frac{e^x - e^{-x}}{e^x + e^{-x}}. \quad (2.3.2)$$

c) **Rectified Linear Unit Function:** The Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) function, shown in Figure 2.3 has been proved to be the most successful and widely used activation function in deep learning. ReLU imposes a non-saturating non-linearity which enhances better gradient flow with improved calculation efficiency (Nwankpa et al., 2018). The range of ReLU lies between 0 and infinity and is mathematically given by Equation 2.3.3.

$$f(x) = \max(0, x) = \begin{cases} x_i, & \text{if } x_i \geq 0 \\ 0, & \text{if } x_i < 0. \end{cases} \quad (2.3.3)$$

Figure 2.3: The sigmoid, tanh and activation functions. Source: (Karn, Accessed October 2019)

d). **Softmax Function:** The softmax function compresses an n-dimensional vector of arbitrary real values to a range of values between 0 and 1 and of probability sum equal to 1. Softmax function is usually used at the output layer to return probability value for each target class of the output values (Nwankpa et al., 2018). The softmax function is defined by Equation 2.3.4.

$$\text{softmax}(z_k^L) = \frac{e^{z_k^L}}{\sum_c e^{z_c^L}}. \quad (2.3.4)$$

2.3.2 Convolutional Layer. The convolutional layer is one of the fundamental layers of CNN. Convolutional layer performs feature extraction on input and aims to learn feature representations of the input. There are two main functions performed in this layer:

a) **Convolution Operation:** The convolution layer takes in an array of pixel values ranging from 0 to 255 as input. The convolution operation helps to extract the features of the input by sifting through the input data to filter out integral parts of the input. During the convolution operation, an array of numbers called kernels (filters) are used as feature extractors. The filters convolve across the input with a chosen number of pixels (stride) for the computation in each location. (O'Shea and Nash, 2015). The element-wise product of the input matrix and the filter is computed and stored in an empty array called a feature map (activation map). The value of the stride determines the exact location for each convolution operation. This procedure is performed continuously with multiple filters. Different computations between the filters and the input array will have a corresponding feature map, which will be stacked to form the full output volume from the convolutional layer (O'Shea and Nash, 2015). Figure 2.4 shows the convolution operation between a 3-dimensional input tensor and three filters.

Mathematically, the discrete convolution between two functions f and g is generally defined by:

$$(f * g)(x) = \sum_t f(t)g(x + t).$$

Given a 2-dimensional input image tensor, the convolution operation between an input array and the filter can be expressed as :

$$(f * g)(i, j) = \sum_m \sum_n f(m, n) g(i - m, j - n),$$

where the input image and the kernel are denoted by f and g respectively. i and j are the indexes of rows and columns of the result matrix. This generalizes to higher dimensions. The size of the feature map is regulated by the following three (3) parameters.

- **Depth:** The depth which is also known as channels is the number of filters used for the convolution operation.
- **Stride:** The stride is the number of pixels by which the kernel is convolved over the input tensor (larger strides produce smaller feature maps).
- **Zero-padding:** Zero-padding involves the insertion of a border of pixels with value zero around the edges of an input image to preserve original input size for avoidance of loss of information.

Figure 2.4: A convolution operation of a 3-Dimensional image tensor with a 3 x 3 kernel size. The kernel is convolved across the input tensor, the dot product yielded a 4 x 4 feature map. Source: (Mesin, Accessed September 2019)

- b) **Non-Linearization:** During non-linearization operation, activation functions, as described in Section 2.3.1 performs a non-linear transformation on the input they receive and send the transformed output to the next layer as input. The normalization operation increases the non-linearity of the network without affecting the receptive fields (region of the input space that affects a particular unit of the network) of the convolutional layer. ReLU activation as described in Section 2.3.1, is often used for non-linear transformations in the hidden layer while the softmax function is commonly used for classification in the output layer.

2.3.3 Subsampling (Pooling) Layer. Pooling reduces the dimensionality of each feature map albeit preserving the best information of each feature within a region (O'Shea and Nash, 2015). The pooling operation involves computing the maximum, average or sum over a small window of the feature map. The small window is applied across an image in different regions determined by a chosen value of stride, and the result is retained as shown in Figure 2.5. Pooling can be of different types:

- **Max Pooling:** The max pooling operation computes the maximum of elements in each region.
- **Average Pooling:** The average pooling operation computes the average of elements in each region.
- **Sum Pooling:** The sum pooling operation computes the sum of all elements in each window.

Figure 2.5: Leftside: A pixel size of $224 \times 224 \times 64$ downsampled to a pixel size of $112 \times 112 \times 64$, Rightside: A 4×4 tensor maxpooled with stride 2 using a 2×2 filter size to produce a 2×2 feature map. Source: (Araujo, Accessed August 2019)

2.3.4 Fully-Connected Layer. The fully-connected layer also known as the dense layer, performs classification based on the features extracted by the other layers. The fully connected layer classifies images by applying the softmax activation function. The output has a probability of numbers ranging from zero to one for each classification label the model is trying to predict.

2.4 Learning Process

The learning process in a deep neural network, refers to the process of optimizing the weights of the network to reduce the error in an algorithm. To measure the progress of a network, an error function is defined to estimate the difference between the targeted output value and the predicted output value. The process of updating the weight and bias values with respect to the error function is implemented using the backpropagation algorithm.

2.4.1 Backpropagation. The backpropagation algorithm aims to understand how a slight change in the values of the weight and bias affect the error function. Through backpropagation, the computation of error terms will proceed backward from the output layers to the input layers iteratively. The values of the weight and bias will be adjusted with each iteration until the error function is minimized. There are many ways in which an error function may be represented. The choice of an error function depends on the choice of user or the type of network to be used. The notations in Table 2.1 will be used in the backpropagation computations.

Notations	
L :	Number of layers, indexed as $l = 1, 2, \dots, L - 1, L$, Nodes in a layer l indexed as $k = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1$, Nodes in a previous layer $l - 1$ indexed as $j = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1$, Nodes in a previous layer $l - 2$ indexed as $i = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1$.
y_k :	The final output of node k in layer L .
E :	The error measured on one input example.
w_{kj}^l :	Weight of the connection of node j in layer $l - 1$ to node k in layer l .
z_k^l :	Weighted sum of activations from the previous layer.
$f(\cdot)$:	Activation function.
a_k^l :	Activated output of a layer.

Table 2.1: Computation Notations

The three major processes involved in the learning process include, forward propagation, backward computation for the output layer and hidden layer as well as weights update.

Forward Propagation is the first step involved in the learning process of a network. An input is fed into the network and propagated forward through the network until it reaches the output layer. For each layer, the weighted sum of an input and a bias shown in Equation 2.4.1 is computed (except for the first input). An activation function as in Equation 2.4.2 is applied to the weighted sum to produce an output to be passed on to the next layer. This process is repeated until the prediction at the output layer is attained.

$$z_k^l = \sum_j w_{kj}^l a_j^{l-1} + b_k^l, \quad (2.4.1)$$

$$a_k^l = f\left(\sum_j w_{kj}^l a_j^{l-1} + b_k^l\right) = f(z_k^l). \quad (2.4.2)$$

Next, we determine how a small change in weights and biases in the network affects the error function by computing the derivatives $\frac{\partial E}{\partial w_{kj}^l}$ and $\frac{\partial E}{\partial b_k^l}$ for both the output layer and the hidden layers. For the output layer, the chain rule will be applied to the error function's partial derivative using Equation 2.4.3

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial w_{kj}^L} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial z_k^L} \cdot \frac{\partial z_k^L}{\partial w_{kj}^L}. \quad (2.4.3)$$

$\frac{\partial E}{\partial z_k^L}$ is the error term denoted as: δ_k^L . From 2.4.1, $\frac{\partial z_k^L}{\partial w_{kj}^L} = a_j^{L-1}$,

$$\text{Hence, } \frac{\partial E}{\partial w_{kj}^L} = \delta_k^L a_j^{L-1}. \quad (2.4.4)$$

Similarly, the chain rule is applied to compute the update for the bias derivatives and is derived thus:

$$\text{Bias Derivative: } \frac{\partial E}{\partial b_k^L} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial z_k^L} \cdot \frac{\partial z_k^L}{\partial b_k^L} = \delta_k^L (1) = \delta_k^L. \quad (2.4.5)$$

Equation 2.4.4 and Equation 2.4.5 represent the derivatives to be used for the update of the output layer. Next, we consider the update for the hidden layer. The update for the hidden layer is computed separately from the output layer since the output layer depends on just the output from the previous layer while update for the hidden layer depends on the output from the previous layer and the input connection to the next layer. Hence, the partial derivatives of the error function for the hidden layers are derived using Equation 2.4.6.

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial w_{ji}^{l-1}} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial a_j^{l-1}} \cdot \frac{\partial a_j^{l-1}}{\partial z_j^{l-1}} \cdot \frac{\partial z_j^{l-1}}{\partial w_{ji}^{l-1}}. \quad (2.4.6)$$

Computing the derivative term by term yields a series of equations. Since the activated output is a function of the weighted sum, the derivative of the error term with respect to the activated output is computed using the chain rule. The second and third terms are computed using Equations 2.4.2 and Equation 2.4.1 respectively. The result of the computations yield Equation 2.4.8.

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial a_j^{l-1}} = \sum_k \frac{\partial E}{\partial z_k^l} \cdot \frac{\partial z_k^l}{\partial a_j^{l-1}} = \sum_k \delta_k^l w_{kj}^l, \quad \frac{\partial a_j^{l-1}}{\partial z_j^{l-1}} = f'(z_j^{l-1}), \quad \frac{\partial z_j^{l-1}}{\partial w_{ji}^{l-1}} = a_i^{l-2}, \quad (2.4.7)$$

$$\text{Thus, } \frac{\partial E}{\partial w_{ji}^{l-1}} = a_i^{l-2} f'(z_j^{l-1}) \sum_k \delta_k^l w_{kj}^l \quad (2.4.8)$$

The error term δ_j^{l-1} can be re-written as: $\delta_j^{l-1} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial a_j^{l-1}} \cdot \frac{\partial a_j^{l-1}}{\partial z_j^{l-1}} = f'(z_j^{l-1}) \sum_k \delta_k^l w_{kj}^l$.

From the computations, the weight and bias derivatives that will be used to update the hidden layer are given by Equation 2.4.9 and Equation 2.4.10 respectively.

$$\text{Hence, Equation 2.4.8 becomes: } \frac{\partial E}{\partial w_{ji}^{l-1}} = a_i^{l-2} \delta_j^{l-1}, \quad (2.4.9)$$

$$\text{For the bias term: } \frac{\partial E}{\partial b_j^{l-1}} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial a_j^{l-1}} \cdot \frac{\partial a_j^{l-1}}{\partial z_j^{l-1}} \cdot \frac{\partial z_j^{l-1}}{\partial b_j^{l-1}} = \delta_j^{l-1} (1) = \delta_j^{l-1}. \quad (2.4.10)$$

These derivatives are used to update the network and they can be applied to an arbitrary number of layers. The generalized form of the derivatives with any activation or error function is given as:

$$\delta_k^l = \frac{\partial E}{\partial z_k^l}, \quad \delta_j^{l-1} = f'(z_j^{l-1}) \sum_k \delta_k^l w_{kj}^l, \quad \frac{\partial E}{\partial w_{jk}^l} = \delta_k^l a_j^{l-1}, \quad \frac{\partial E}{\partial b_k^l} = \delta_k^l.$$

The error computed in a layer depends on the error in the next layer. Thus, the error flows backward and the weight and bias values are updated for all layers. An optimization algorithm is used to update the values of the weights and the bias. A commonly used optimization algorithm is the stochastic gradient descent.

The stochastic gradient descent estimates the gradient from a small sample of randomly chosen training input in each iteration, called mini-batches. The gradient of an error function is used to find the global minima for the minimization of the error function. The weights and bias values are updated using Equation 2.4.11 and Equation 2.4.12 respectively, where α is the learning rate. The learning rate α is the step size taken by the gradient descent at each iteration.

$$\Delta w_{kj} \leftarrow w_{kj} - \alpha \frac{\partial E}{\partial w_{kj}}, \quad (2.4.11)$$

$$\Delta b_k \leftarrow b_k - \alpha \frac{\partial E}{\partial b_k}. \quad (2.4.12)$$

2.4.2 Regularization Techniques. A deep neural network can produce great results if provided with a large dataset for training. Consequently, if the dataset is insufficient, the network tends to overfit or underfit on the training set. Overfitting occurs when a neural network is closely fitted to the training data and fails to generalize and make useful predictions on new data (Nusrat and Jang, 2018). Similarly, underfitting occurs when there is insufficient data for the model to learn. To avoid overfitting and underfitting in a network, some regularization techniques discussed in this section. These techniques have been proposed to modify an algorithm to aid better generalization and improve a model's performance.

a) **L1/L2 Regularization:** L1 and L2 regularization techniques reduce overfitting in a network by penalizing the loss function as shown in Equation 2.4.13 and 2.4.14 respectively. The loss function is updated by the addition of a regularization term which regulates the values of the weight matrices (Krogh and Hertz, 1992). The regulation parameter λ modulates how strongly weights are penalized and can be optimized for better results.

L1 regularization adds an absolute magnitude of coefficient as a penalty term to the loss function to reduce weight values of less important features in the network. L2 regularization adds the squared

magnitude of coefficient as a penalty term to the loss function. These regularization terms can both be used or employed separately to improve a network's performance.

$$\text{L1} : w^* = \text{Loss}(y, \hat{y}) + \lambda \sum_{i=1}^k |w_i|, \quad (2.4.13)$$

$$\text{L2} : w^* = \text{Loss}(y, \hat{y}) + \lambda \sum_{i=1}^k (w_i)^2. \quad (2.4.14)$$

- b) **Batch Normalization:** The normalization of an input data to have zero mean and unit variance is often implemented to speed up the learning process of a network. Batch normalization is a regularization technique proposed by [Szegedy et al. \(2016\)](#) to further improve the generalization ability of a network by applying normalization to each hidden layer. The batch normalization technique is executed by applying normalization to every value from the preceding layer before it is passed on to the next layer ([Szegedy et al., 2016](#)). Each value passed on to the batch normalization layer represents a batch of values to be normalized. The normalization process is described thus:

Given values z^l from a previous layer for each observation i in a dataset. The mean and variance is computed as

$$\mu = \frac{1}{n} \sum_i z_i^l, \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_i (z_i^l - \mu)^2.$$

Using these values, z^l is normalized as $z_{norm}^{(i)} = \frac{z^{(i)} - \mu}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + \epsilon}}$,

ϵ : small number to prevent zero division

Practically, restriction of activation values to zero mean and unit variance could limit the network's optimal performance. Thus, parameters γ and β are applied to scale normalized values by α and shift by β such that $\tilde{z}^{(i)} = \gamma z_{norm}^{(i)} + \beta$

- c) **Drop-Out:** Dropout is another regularization technique proposed by [Srivastava et al. \(2014\)](#), used to improve a network's learning capability. The dropout process can be applied to both the input layer and the hidden layers. [Srivastava et al. \(2014\)](#) describe the technique as a process of random selection of some nodes which are dropped out of the network with a chosen probability ' p ' during the training process. By dropping a unit out, all its incoming and outgoing connections are temporarily removed. The dropout process is performed iteratively, each with different nodes to be dropped out and formally dropped out nodes restored. By repeating this process, each node learns independently of other nodes and increases the optimal performance of the network.
- d) **Data Augmentation:** One of the major challenges in the training implementation in a deep neural network is the lack of sufficient datasets for training the network. Data augmentation can reduce overfitting and underfitting by artificially creating new data samples through transformation. The technique increases the size of the training data by the generation of relevant samples in various orientations and sizes ([Abdelhafiz et al., 2019](#)). The transformation process includes image rotation, scaling, shifting, flipping e.t.c. In general, data augmentation increases a network's ability to generalize well.

2.5 CNN Models

CNN models of varying structures have been developed to solve image classification problem. Discussed in this section are three CNN models that achieved state-of-the-art performance in an ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge. The ImageNet dataset consists of 1.2 million images with 1000 classes. The CNN models described in this section achieved the highest accuracy in the classification of the images contained in the ImageNet dataset (Simonyan and Zisserman, 2014).

2.5.1 Visual Geometry Group (VGG). VGG is a deep convolutional neural network published by Simonyan and Zisserman (2014), researchers from Oxford University, to analyze the effect of increasing the depth of a deep neural network with multiple 3×3 convolution filters in each convolutional layer (Tsochatzidis et al., 2019). The VGG architecture shown in Figure 2.6 receives an input size of 224×224 . VGG architecture is composed of 5 blocks of stacked convolutional layers with max-pooling performed over a 2×2 pixel window and three fully connected layers. The first two fully-connected layers are 4096 channels each, while the last layer performs the classification task (Simonyan and Zisserman, 2014). Multiple configurations were performed for 11, 13, 16 and 19 layers. The most commonly used architectures are the VGG16 (16 layers) and VGG19 (19 layers).

Figure 2.6: The architecture of VGG16.

2.5.2 Residual Networks (ResNet). ResNet is a convolutional neural network proposed by (He et al., 2015), a Microsoft research team. He et al. (2015) proposed ResNet to address the difficulty encountered in training a network with too many layers by the implementation of a skip connection also known as shortcut connections. By the introduction of these skip connections, one or more layers are skipped and the output of one layer is fed to the output of the layer after the skipped layers (He et al., 2015). An illustration of the skip connection is depicted in Figure 2.7. The skip connections increase the training ability of a network and allows deeper network without an increase in error rate. The architecture was tested for varying depths. Figure 2.8 shows a 34-layered ResNet with skip connections. A ResNet model can either have a two-layer deep skip connection or a three-layer deep skip connection. ResNet50 has 50 layers with a three layer deep skip connection. After each convolutional layer in a ResNet50 network, the batch normalization layer (Section 2.4.2) is included.

Figure 2.7: A skip connection for the ResNet. Source: (Mesin, Accessed September 2019)

Figure 2.8: A 34 layered ResNet architecture showing the implementation of skip connections throughout the network. Source: (Mesin, Accessed September 2019)

2.5.3 InceptionV3. InceptionV3 is a convolutional neural network model formulated by the Google research team, Szegedy et al. (2016). The researchers aimed to create a less computationally complex model with an increased performance level. The first implementation was the GoogleNet with inception module which consisted of four concatenated 1×1 , 3×3 and 5×5 convolutional filters with 3×3 max pool. The first 1×1 filter performs convolution for linear transformation on input. The second and third filters perform 1×1 convolution for dimensionality reduction followed by a 3×3 and 5×5 convolution respectively. Max-pooling is then performed, followed by a 1×1 operation (Chougrad et al., 2018). A standard inception block is shown in Figure 2.9. GoogleNet which was the first proposed model is constructed by stacking nine inception modules. InceptionV3 was designed as an improvement over previously proposed models (Chougrad et al., 2018). The batch normalization technique (Section 2.4.2) was introduced in the network, to increase the learning rate of the network. Figure 2.10 shows a complete stack of inception modules to form an Inception network. The InceptionV3 network has a total of 11 stacked inception modules.

Figure 2.9: Structure of one Inception Module.

Figure 2.10: A stack of inception modules form a full Inception Network. Source: (Alexis, Accessed October 2019)

3. Methodology

In this chapter, we will describe the general processes involved in the experiment. The processes include image preprocessing, transfer learning, validation techniques, and evaluation criteria.

Two different experiments will be performed using different datasets. A binary classification task will be performed on the first set of mammogram images for the detection of normal and abnormal tumors using three CNN models. In addition to this, a multiclass classification task will be performed on a larger dataset. The CNN models will be refined to perform a five-way classification for normal, benign and malignant tumors. Figure 3.1 shows the flowchart of steps for the two experiments.

Figure 3.1: Experiment Flowchart for the MIAS and DDSM datasets

3.1 Datasets

Two public datasets gotten from Kaggle database were used for the experiments. Each of the datasets contains labeled normal and abnormal tumors from mammogram images as will be described in this section.

3.1.1 MIAS. The Mammographic Image Analysis Society (MIAS) database ¹ contains 322 cases, of which 207 are normal and 115 abnormal (63 benign and 51 malignant). The database consists of left and right breast images of 161 patients. The size of all the images is 1024×1024 pixels, all of which have been centered in the matrix. The images also include the radiologist’s truth markings on the location of any abnormalities that may be present (abnormalities such as architectural distortions, calcifications, stellate lesions, and circumscribed mass). Figure 3.2a and Figure 3.2b show samples of normal and abnormal images from the MIAS database.

¹MIAS Dataset: <https://www.kaggle.com/kmader/mias-mammography>

Figure 3.2: Normal and abnormal tumor view of two MIAS Images

3.1.2 DDSM / CBIS-DDSM. The Digital Database for Screening Mammography (DDSM)² contains approximately 2,620 studies of normal and abnormal tumors. The Curated Breast Imaging Subset of DDSM (CBIS-DDSM) is an updated and standardized version of DDSM. (Scuccimarra (Accessed September 2019) created a whole dataset to contain mixed pre-processed images from DDSM and CBIS-DDSM). The compiled dataset consists of 55,872 training samples of approximately 14% normal and 86% abnormal cases. Classes for the images are Normal (**N**) - 48,583 cases, Benign Calcification (**BC**) - 2,103 cases, Benign Mass (**BM**) - 1911 cases, Malignant Calcification (**MC**) - 1463 cases and Malignant Mass (**MM**) - 1812 cases. Figure 3.3 shows samples of all five cases extracted from the database.

Figure 3.3: Normal, Malignant and Benign Tumors from the DDSM/CBIS-DDSM database.

3.2 Image Pre-Processing

The presence of artifacts and noise can hinder breast cancer detection and reduce a model's accuracy in predicting. Hence, it is necessary to process the images to improve a model's performance. Preprocessing techniques eliminate artifacts, reduce noise and enhance the contrast of an image. Image enhancement and segmentation are the pre-processing techniques for this experiment.

3.2.1 Image Enhancement. The image enhancement technique improves the contrast of an image and reduces noise. The Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) is an image enhancement technique that adopts histogram equalization for contrast improvement. Histogram equalization

²DDSM Dataset: <https://www.kaggle.com/skooch/ddsm-mammography>

adjusts the pixels of an image to an equal range. CLAHE technique is summarized thus. Each image is divided into regions or small blocks of equal sizes, histogram equalization is applied to each image block. To avoid noise amplification, the histogram is limited by a clip level which is distributed uniformly among the histogram.

3.2.2 Image Segmentation. Image Segmentation technique separates an image into regions with similar features such as color or intensity. Segmentation of an image gives a meaningful representation of the image for easy analysis (Abdelhafiz et al., 2019). The adaptive mean threshold method of segmentation is a technique used to remove artifacts from the images. Adaptive thresholding takes an image and converts it to a binary image separated into foreground and background pixels. While background pixels are set to black, foreground pixels are set to white. The background or foreground choice is determined by a chosen threshold value (Mina and Isa, 2014). The adaptive mean threshold value calculates the threshold of a pixel as the mean of a local neighborhood. If a pixel value is below the threshold, it is set to background value, otherwise it is set to foreground value.

3.3 Dataset Split/ Validation Techniques

To train a neural network model, we need techniques to measure and validate the performance of the model. Several measures can be used to evaluate the performance of a CNN model. In this section, we describe some validation techniques that can be used to measure the efficiency of a model.

Cross-validation is a statistical technique that is used to evaluate predictive models (Refaeilzadeh et al., 2009). There are three common types of cross-validation technique:

- **Hold-out split:** The hold-out method splits the original sample into a training set and a test set. The training set is used to train the model and the test set estimates the error rate of the trained model.
- **Three-way data splits:** The three-way-data split partitions the original sample data into a training set, validation set, and a test set. The training set is used to train the model to fit parameters of the classifier and the validation set is used to tune hyperparameters like learning rate and batch size. The model's performance is evaluated using the test set.
- **K -folds cross-validation:** For the k -fold split, the original data sample is split into k subsets or folds. The ' $K-1$ ' subsets are used to train the network K times, each of the K sets is used once as the test set till all samples in the dataset are used for both training and testing exactly once. K error estimates from the folds are averaged to produce a single estimator.

3.4 Transfer Learning and Fine-Tuning

3.4.1 Transfer Learning. Transfer learning is the application of deep learning models that have been trained on a large dataset to smaller dataset for another problem, by transferring the weights learned during previous training to a new training process. The CNN models described in Section 2.5 have been pre-trained on an ImageNet dataset that contains 1.2 million images. The weights learned during the training process can be transferred to another problem to save computational cost and time. The transfer learning technique will be applied to the breast cancer dataset using the pre-trained CNN models. We can apply the transfer learning technique in several ways some of which include feature extraction, fine-tuning, and freezing certain layers whilst re-training other layers. We will apply transfer learning in this experiment by fine-tuning the last few layers of the models. This will be achieved by modifying the last few layers and keeping the weights of the initial layers of the pre-trained network.

3.4.2 Fine-Tuning Hyperparameters. Hyperparameters refer to the variables that are set before the training process commences. Hyper-parameters play a significant role in the optimal performance of a network. Accordingly, we need to tune these hyper-parameters to boost the performance of our models. Four major hyperparameters that will be tuned for these experiments include the learning rate, the number of epochs, the batch size, and the choice of activation functions (discussed in Section 2.3.1).

- **Learning Rate:** The learning rate is the step size taken by the optimization algorithm at each iteration. The appropriate learning rate must be chosen to avoid a long training time for too small learning rates, and divergence of the loss values in the network.
- **Batch Size:** The batch size is the number of samples from the training set to be propagated through the network before the update of the internal parameters (weights and biases). A large batch size could lead to poor generalization and a small batch size could boost convergence. A well-adopted value of batch size is 32.
- **Number of Epochs:** The number of epochs measures the number of times all the training vectors are used once to update the weights iteratively. A good way of tracking the number of epochs is to observe or keep record of the validation loss. If the validation loss, keeps decreasing, the training can proceed further. However, if the validation error starts increasing, the training process should be terminated.

3.5 Evaluation Criteria

After training a CNN model, evaluative performance measures are implemented to access the predictive model's performance on test data. The techniques described in the following subsections are used to measure the efficiency of a predictive model in performing prediction.

3.5.1 Confusion Matrix. A confusion matrix, also known as an error matrix, is used to summarize the performance of a classification model. The matrix contains information about the actual and predicted classification done by a classification system (Kohavi and Provost, 1998). Table 3.1 represents the entries of a 2×2 and 5×5 confusion matrices.

		Predicted	
		Positive	Negative
Actual	Positive	TP	FN
	Negative	FP	TN

		Predicted				
		A	B	C	D	E
Actual	A	TP_A	E _{AB}	E _{AC}	E _{AD}	E _{AE}
	B	E _{BA}	TP_B	E _{BC}	E _{BD}	E _{BE}
	C	E _{CA}	E _{CB}	TP_C	E _{CD}	E _{CE}
	D	E _{DA}	E _{DB}	E _{DC}	TP_D	E _{DE}
	E	E _{EA}	E _{EB}	E _{EC}	E _{ED}	TP_E

Table 3.1: 2×2 and 5×5 Confusion Matrices

Notations: In general,

- True Positive (TP): Instances of samples correctly classified as positive.
- True Negative (TN): Instances of samples correctly classified as negative.
- False Positive (FP): Instances of samples incorrectly classified as positive.
- False Negative (FN): Instances of samples incorrectly classified as negative.

For the 5×5 confusion matrix:

- FN: Sum of values in the corresponding class row minus the TP value.
- FP: Sum of values in the corresponding class column minus the TP value.
- TN: Sum of all rows and columns except the corresponding classes' row and column.
- E_{AB} : Class A incorrectly classified as B (This applies to other notations in the matrix) ...

From the confusion matrix, the following performance metrics can be computed: (i) is for the 2×2 matrix, and (ii) is the computation for the 5×5 matrix.

3.5.2 Accuracy. This measures the percentage of the total number of correct predictions.

$$\text{i) Accuracy} = \frac{TP + FN}{\text{Total Samples}}, \quad \text{ii) Accuracy} = \frac{TP}{\text{Total Samples}}.$$

3.5.3 Recall/Sensitivity. This measures the proportion of positive cases that were correctly classified.

$$\text{i) Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{Total Actual Positive}}, \quad \text{ii) Recall A} = \frac{TP_A}{TN_A + E_{BA} + E_{CA} + E_{DA} + E_{EA}} \dots$$

3.5.4 Precision. This measures the proportion of predicted positive cases that were correct.

$$\text{i) Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{Total Predicted Positive}}, \quad \text{ii) Precision A} = \frac{TP_A}{TP_A + E_{BA} + E_{CA} + E_{DA} + E_{EA}} \dots$$

3.5.5 F1 Score. This measures the harmonic mean of the precision and recall values of a classification problem.

$$F1 = \frac{\text{recall}^{-1} + \text{precision}^{-1}}{2} = 2 * \left\{ \frac{\text{precision} \times \text{recall}}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}} \right\}$$

4. Experiments

This chapter presents the preprocessing techniques on the datasets, as well as the CNN models applied on the dataset. This chapter also presents the results of these models.

4.1 Breast Cancer Prediction for Binary Classification (Experiment I)

4.1.1 MIAS Image Pre-processing. The images in the MIAS dataset were pre-processed using the pre-processing techniques described in Section 3.2. The contrast of the images was enhanced using the CLAHE technique. In addition to this, the threshold technique was applied to the images for noise reduction and the removal of the artifacts as can be seen in Figure 4.1a. After pre-processing the images, we get a better sample of images to be used for training. Figure 4.1b is a sample of a resulting image after pre-processing.

Figure 4.1: MIAS image before and after pre-processing

4.1.2 Splitting of MIAS images. The MIAS dataset is classified into normal and abnormal tumors. For the training process, we divided the dataset using the three-way data split described in Section 3.3. For a balanced distribution of both normal and abnormal tumors in the train, validation and test sets, we sub-divided the normal and abnormal tumors in a ratio of 70:15:15 respectively. The normal and abnormal tumors for each dataset were well represented in each set according to the specified ratio. After splitting, we had 224 samples in the training set, 48 samples in the validation set and 50 samples in the test set.

4.1.3 Fine-tuning. The pre-trained CNN models described in Section 2.5 are the models we implemented for the training of our dataset. In general, the first few convolutional blocks of a CNN model learn low level-features such as shape and edges. The features learned can be generalized to different images. In line with this, we used the transfer learning technique, as described in Section 3.4, to extract features from the pre-trained CNN models. Furthermore, we fine-tuned the top-layers of the model to make predictions on the MIAS dataset.

The transfer learning and fine-tuning processes were implemented using the Keras deep learning framework,¹ with Tensorflow² as the backend in python. The first step was to import the saved weights of the pre-trained models. We then built a classifier model on top of the convolutional blocks of the pre-trained CNN models. The classifier model included the addition of a global spatial average pooling layer (Section 2.3.3), a dropout layer (Section 2.4.2), a fully connected layer (Section 2.3.4) and an output layer for binary classification.

¹Keras library is available in: <https://keras.io/>

²Tensorflow library is available in: <https://www.tensorflow.org/>

We trained the top layers (classifier model) which was randomly initialized. We did the training by freezing the convolutional layers of the pre-trained CNN models. The reason for freezing the base layers (layers before the top layers) of the classifier was to avoid the elimination of the weights previously learned by the model due to the backpropagation of the error. The top classifier was trained with a chosen number of epochs. After training the top classifier, we proceeded to fine-tune the model.

We implemented fine-tuning by training the top layers of the model. Since the base layers of the models already learned useful features, we froze all the convolutional blocks except the last convolutional block for training because the top layers learn only data-specific features. The experiment for each CNN model is described in Section 4.1.4

4.1.4 Experiment I. The MIAS images were rescaled automatically to a size of 224×224 to make the images compatible with the ImageNet size. For this experiment, we implemented the VGG16, InceptionV3 and ResNet50 CNN models for the training process. The stochastic gradient descent was used as the optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0001. The three models were fine-tuned as described in Section 4.1.3. For fine-tuning, the first 15 convolutional layers of the VGG16 model were frozen, while the last convolutional layer and the fully connected layers were trained using the stochastic gradient descent optimizer. Similarly, the first 265 layers of the Inception module was frozen, while the last two inception modules and the fully connected layers were trained. Lastly, the first 125 layers of the ResNet model were also frozen and the last two convolutional layers and fully connected layers were trained. For the feature extraction process, the top classifier was trained with a chosen batch size of 8, for 10 epochs, and 50 epochs for the fine-tuning process (the optimal hyperparameter values were selected after multiple trials). The training time for the InceptionV3 and ResNet50 models was approximately 50 mins each while the VGG16 model trained for approximately 1.5 hours for 50 epochs.

4.1.5 Results and Discussion. The performance of each CNN model was evaluated using the confusion matrix, accuracy, precision, and recall. Figure 4.3a, 4.3b, and Figure 4.3c show the graphical representation of the training and validation accuracies with respect to the number of epochs for the InceptionV3, ResNet50 and VGG16 models respectively. The ResNet50 gave the best result with an accuracy of 68%. The models did not perform well on the MIAS dataset due to the small number of images contained in the dataset. Despite using transfer learning and fine-tuning techniques, the models did not yield high accuracy.

Besides the small amount of samples in the dataset, an unbalanced number of image samples also influenced the performance of the models. The confusion matrix in Figure 4.3a shows that the model was more biased towards learning more of the positive cases than the negative cases due to the imbalance in the dataset. VGG16 and InceptionV3 had a 64% accuracy. The InceptionV3 and VGG16 model failed to learn from the abnormal datasets but only correctly predicted the normal samples with a 100% recall as shown in Table 4.1. ResNet50 could correctly identify 3 as TP and 31 as TN. Figure 4.2 and Table 4.1 show confusion matrix and the values of precision, recall, and f1 score for all three models.

Inception V3	Precision	Recall	F1 score
Abnormal	0%	0%	0%
Normal	64%	100%	78%

VGG16	Precision	Recall	F1 score
Abnormal	0%	0%	0%
Normal	64%	100%	78%

ResNet50	Precision	Recall	F1 score
Abnormal	75%	17%	27%
Normal	67%	97%	79%

Table 4.1: Evaluation Metrics for InceptionV3, VGG16 and ResNet50 models.

Figure 4.2: The Confusion Matrix for each of the models.

Figure 4.3: Training and Validation accuracies per epoch.

4.2 Breast Cancer Prediction for Multiclass Classification (Experiment II)

4.2.1 DDSM-CBIS Image Pre-processing. The images in the DDSM-CBIS dataset were pre-processed by Scuccimarra (Accessed September 2019). Some of the pre-processing techniques involved the extraction of Region of Interests (ROIs) and re-sizing each image to 299×299 . The dataset which consists of negative and positive images from DDSM and CBIS datasets respectively, had their ROIs extracted using masks with a small amount of padding to provide context (Scuccimarra, Accessed September 2019). Figure 4.4 shows a sample of a pre-processed image in the dataset.

Figure 4.4: Sample of pre-processed DDSM/CBIS Image.

4.2.2 Splitting of DDSM-CBIS images. The DDSM-CBIS dataset has five classes, described in Section 3.1.2. For the training process, we divided the dataset using the three-way data split described in Section 3.3. To ensure a good representation of all five classes in the train, validation and test sets, we divided the overall sample of images in the ratio 50:25:25. After splitting, the train set consisted of 27,934 samples, the validation set consisted of 13,969 samples and the test set consisted of 13,969 samples. Each of the five classes were evenly subdivided and well-represented in all three sets.

4.2.3 Fine-tuning. The transfer learning and fine-tuning processes are as described for the MIAS experiment in Section 4.1.3. The convolutional layers of the pre-trained CNN models were frozen, with the top classifier trained. After training the top classifier, the models were fine-tuned to predict images for five classes. The stochastic gradient descent was used with a learning rate of 0.0001.

4.2.4 Experiment II. For this experiment, we evaluated the performance of the InceptionV3 and ResNet models on the five classes contained in the given dataset. The top classifier was trained for 4 epochs. The last convolutional layer and the fully connected layers were further trained for 20 epochs with a batch size of 100. The performance of each model was evaluated with the confusion matrix, accuracy, precision, recall, and specificity. The training time for the InceptionV3 and ResNet50 models was approximately 24 hours each for 20 epochs while the VGG16 model trained for approximately 48 hours for 20 epochs.

4.2.5 Results and Discussion. The InceptionV3 model performed best in the prediction of all five classes in the test set. InceptionV3 had an accuracy of 87%. The values of precision, recall and f1 score are shown in Table 4.2. The InceptionV3 model's bad performance in predicting the BC class could be attributed to a low number of samples that belong to the BC class. The model achieved high accuracy in correctly predicting the normal cases due to the high number of normal cases in the dataset. Figure 4.5 shows a graphical representation of the training and validation accuracy per epoch.

Similarly, the correctly classified normal instances in the implementation of ResNet50 model superseded the correct classification of other classes with an accuracy of 85%. Table 4.2 shows the values of the precision, recall and f1 scores of the ResNet50 model for each of the classes. Figure 4.5b shows the graphical representation of the training and validation accuracies per epoch. A summary of the confusion matrix for each model is shown in Table 4.2

(a) InceptionV3
Training-Validation
accuracy per epoch.

(b) ResNet50
Training-Validation
accuracy per epoch.

Figure 4.5: Graphical Representation of Training and Validation Accuracy per epoch for each model.

(a) DDSM-CBIS Confusion Matrix for InceptionV3 model.

(b) ResNet50 confusion matrix for DDSM-CBIS dataset.

Figure 4.6: Confusion Matrices for the InceptionV3 and ResNet50 models.

InceptionV3	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
N	88%	100%	93%
BC	38%	1%	2%
BM	46%	2%	4%
MC	0%	0%	0%
MM	48%	11%	18%

ResNet50	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
N	87%	98%	92%
BC	5%	0%	0%
BM	3%	0%	0%
MC	0%	0%	0%
MM	0%	0%	0%

Table 4.2: Precision, Recall and F1 score values for the DDSM-CBIS Experiment.

4.2.6 Additional Experiment. To further test a model's ability to correctly classify with a balanced dataset, we subsampled the normal tumors to 7000 samples of images. All other abnormal tumors were concatenated to form abnormal samples containing approximately 7000 images. The normal and abnormal tumors were split into train, validation and test sets in the ratio 70:15:15. The VGG16 model was then implemented to perform a binary classification on the DDSM/CBIS dataset and was trained for a total of 24 epochs with a batch size of 100. The model had an accuracy of 86%. The VGG16 model's precision, recall and f1 score shown in Table 4.3. Figure 4.7a shows the training and validation accuracy of the VGG16 model with respect to the number of epochs and Figure 4.7b shows the Confusion matrix for the VGG16 model.

VGG16	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
Abnormal	100%	73%	84%
Normal	78%	100%	88%
Avg.	89%	86%	86%

Table 4.3: Precision, Recall and F1 score values for the VGG16 Experiment.

(a) VGG16 Training-Validation Accuracy per epoch

(b) Confusion Matrix for the VGG16 model

Figure 4.7: Experimental Results for the VGG16 model Using Subsampled Datasets

4.3 General Discussion

In general, we observed that the number of samples contained in the MIAS dataset had a colossal effect on the predictive performance of the models. In addition to this, the dataset contained more of normal cases than abnormal cases. The unbalanced effect tilted the model towards learning more of the normal cases than the abnormal cases.

For the DDSM-CBIS experiment, the number of epochs and batch size influenced the predictive performance of the models. Due to lack of computational power and time, the number of epochs was set to 20 and the batch size to 100. Training for a larger number of epochs would have given the model more time to learn from the dataset.

Furthermore, there was a high imbalance in the samples of each class for the CBIS-DDSM dataset. We had 86% of normal cases, and approximately 3% of each of the abnormal classes (BC, BM, MC, and MM). This high level of imbalance created an adverse effect on the predictive performance of the model and this led to a biased performance by each of the models.

To prove this further, we subsampled the normal subset to 7000 samples and merged the abnormal tumors to approximately 7000 samples to have a balanced dataset. Even with the small number of instances in the dataset, the VGG16 model was able to accurately classify 86% of the images with high precision, recall and f1 scores as shown in Table 4.3. Hence, a balanced dataset, number of samples and computational power are three major factors that affect the predictive performance of a model.

3 4

³All the codes used to perform the experiments and more are available in: <https://github.com/Staritino/Deep-Learning-for-Breast-Cancer-Prediction.git>

⁴Computations were performed using facilities provided by the University of Cape Town's ICTS High Performance Computing team: hpc.uct.ac.za

5. Conclusion and Future Work

In this essay, we studied the application of deep learning in the prediction of breast cancer. The main objective of this essay was to evaluate the predictive performance of three pre-trained CNN models in the detection of breast tumors from mammogram images. Two different datasets composed of varying numbers of samples were utilized for our experiment. The InceptionV3, VGG16, and ResNet50 were trained on both datasets for binary classification and multiclass classification.

The ResNet50 model achieved the highest predictive performance on the test set for the MIAS dataset with an accuracy of 68%. On the other hand, the InceptionV3 model performed best on the DDSM-CBIS dataset with an accuracy of 87%. Indeed, the performance of each model was greatly influenced by the number of epochs, batch size and the unbalanced number of samples in each dataset. Due to lack of computational resources and time, the number of epochs for which each model was trained and batch sizes were reduced. The models also performed better in the prediction of normal cases in both datasets due to the very high number of normal samples in each dataset.

The VGG16 model was used as a predictive model to test imbalance in a dataset. The DDSM/CBIS dataset was subsampled and merged into two sets. The VGG16 model performed binary classification and attained an accuracy of 86%. This showed how well a model performs on a balanced dataset.

In general, lack of computational resources and an unbalanced dataset are two major problems that are usually encountered in deep learning for medical imaging. With the advent and growth of computational resources, we are certain that these problems will be addressed.

A possible extension to this work in the future could be the concatenation of the CNN models to form an ensemble for breast cancer prediction. Also, we could implement this ensemble model in determining the recurrence of breast cancer in a patient in the space of five years or more.

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